

ZERO-COPY MERGE FOR ROOT RNTUPLE

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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Data sets in High-Energy Physics (HEP) are often produced in a parallel manner where tens or hundreds of processes produce partial results that are merged into a single file at the end of the data processing workflow. This is enabled by the parallel nature of HEP data, where individual collisions can be processed independently from each other. The predominant file format for storing HEP data is provided by the ROOT libraries. Modern file systems allow for zero-copy cloning of data blocks. This feature has a potentially high impact for the merging of HEP data, as it may allow creation of merged results without physically copying the partial results. The aim of this project is to evaluate the zero-copy merging functionality in modern file systems as well as the requirements to use it at the file format level (e.g., relocatability). The results of this project have an impact on ROOT's object store support as well, as HEP data in object stores such as Intel DAOS is by nature prepared to exploit zero-copy merging.

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1 INTRODUCTION

As the volume of data generated by High Energy Physics (HEP) events is rapidly increasing, it is crucial having a software stack that can take advantage of the modern hardware such as NVM device. `ROOT RNTuple` is a columnar I/O subsystem developed to analyze the significant amount of data generated to HEP events exploiting the state-of-the-art hardware and storage system. It is a backward-incompatible redesign of `ROOT TTree`, the I/O subsystem traditionally used to store the large amount of data related to HEP events [2]. `RNTuple` encodes HEP events as records, and these records are stored on disk following a columnar layout. Each file contains a different range of events and often a merging operation is needed to extend the analysis to a wider event-span. This can be performed through a merging operation. This operation - when applied to a such amount of data - often requires a large amount of resources, in term of space and time. Therefore, optimizing this operation is crucial to enable a more efficient data analysis.

In this work we provide an extensive analysis of the challenges related to the implementation of an efficient merging algorithm of `RNTuples`. We contribute with a first implementation of zero-copy merge and we compare it with other different possible implementations. Finally, we provide an overview of those aspects related to this algorithm that still need to be investigated.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 REFLINKS and Block Sharing

Our zero-copy merge algorithm builds on the concept of `reflink`, i.e. blocks sharing between files at file system level. The idea behind this mechanism is that it is more convenient to copy a file by sharing the file system blocks already allocated to that file by making the replica pointing to the blocks of source file. One of the file systems making this feature available to the user is `btrfs`. It implements a copy-on-write mechanism which allows to quickly duplicate a file by making the destination file pointing to the file-blocks of the source file. Despite this mechanism seems similar to the `hardlink` mechanism typically available on any file system, it differs for two main reasons. First, this cloning feature works with a finer granularity, allowing to share only some of the file-blocks. Second, each file has its own metadata, i.e. different inodes. Moreover, it allows files to share the same blocks as long as the blocks are identical. If any modification happens to the source file, `btrfs` will provide to duplicate only blocks which are modified in order to preserve the integrity of the original file.

It is clear then this blocks sharing technique comes with several advantages. In first instance, it reduces the sharing granularity from the whole file to the file block. It allows to share some blocks only and duplicate some other which are going to be different. Then, it allows to keep different metadata for different files, i.e. a file has its own inode but same blocks of other files. In addition to this, it allows to save space on the device as no additional blocks are allocated per file. Finally, the full copy of a file is basically immediate, as blocks are only shared rather than copied.

This feature is exposed to the user by means of the `ioctl` system call, which allows to zero-copy either the whole file or a specified byte range within the file. Despite the many advantages of this system call, this mechanism is not free from limitations. (1) The address range cannot be arbitrary; it needs to be aligned to the whole file. If the range is not aligned, the system call fails and no block is shared or copied. (2) If the file system does not support the `reflink` feature, the system call fails when called. (3) To our knowledge, this system call is available only on Linux.

Although these limitations, `ioctl` system call represents the starting point of this work.

2.2 ROOT7 and RNTuples

Data coming from HEP events are encoded as records having a certain number of properties. However, the workload related to the analysis of these data often only requires to access a subset of these features [1]. Given this characteristic, both ROOT TTree and its successor ROOT RNTuple adopted a columnar layout to store data on disk, as it allows to efficiently access only a subset of attributes for a certain range of events. At very high level, the structure of RNTuple on disk can be described as in Figure 1. Each events has a set of attributes, which we can see as fixed or variable-length columns. As RNTuple data are stored in a file following a columnar layout, each column for all the events are stored one after the other. One or more columns are stored in pages, which contain the compressed representation of the original data. The page size usually extends to few tens of kilobytes. Pages are further grouped in clusters, which gather data for a specific event range. In the end, clusters can be grouped in clusters groups. In a RNTuple there is always at least one cluster group. Every cluster group is followed by a `page list`, which contains the offsets of the cluster pages. Finally, a `header` and a `footer` wrap the RNTuple. The `header` contains the schema of the RNTuple; while the `footer` contains information about clusters, cluster groups, etc. Header, footer and page lists represent the metadata for the RNTuple they refer to.

Figure 1: RNTuple on-disk physical layout [1]

3 DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, we describe the main design challenges and choices that led us to the current implementation of our zero-copy merge algorithm. In general, the merge of RNTuples is the concatenation of the content - pages, clusters and clusters group - of an arbitrary number of RNTuple files. This merge can be `trivial`, when data are read from disk, decompressed, added to the new RNTuple, compressed back and written in a new file. Despite its implementation is pretty naive, as there is no need to manually update metadata, it results in being quite inefficient, as we pay the cost of decompression and compression in addition to read/write. Thus, we can avoid decompression and compression by reading the content from the source files and writing it directly on the third file. We call this implementation `fast-merge`. Finally, rather than reading/writing the columns from the source RNTuple files, we can share directly the blocks these files are made of. This is allowed on file systems such as `btrfs` or `XFS` that implement the `reflink` mechanism we mentioned in Section 2.1. This will result in an almost constant merging time, where no read and write is necessary. We refers to this implementation as `zero-copy merge`. The latter is the objective of this work. More specifically, given `n`-files

storing n-RNTuples, we want to generate a new file, having a new header and footer, but the same clusters structure of the source files. The merging algorithm of RNTuple is structured as follows. In first instance, we need to deal with the address alignment limitations affecting every `relink` implementation currently available, in order to enable the block sharing mechanism. Then, we need to actually copy or share the columns between RNTuples. Finally, we need to update the metadata, i.e. the column offsets with respect to the destination RNTuple.

3.1 RNTuple Padding

In order to make working the `relink` mechanism, we need to align the RNTuples data chunks to the file system block size. In order to achieve that, we add some padding when an RNTuple is first created. Then, we assume that when RNTuples are used, they will already have the right padding to enable the efficient merging. The typical file block size in many file system is 4KB, so in our implementation we assume that as default block size. The padding is added in three points within a RNTuple file. The first RNTuple element to be padded is the header. We extend the header to match the closest, higher, 4K-aligned address. This will assure that the cluster pages starts at a block-aligned address. A second padding is added when a cluster group is committed, i.e. is written on disk. At the end of each cluster group a page list is added to the file. A page list, contains the offsets that allows to access the element in the previous clusters. Thus, this second padding written between the last page of cluster group and the page list assures that data content is extended until the end of the data block. Once the page list is written, a new cluster group is created. At this point, what we need is that also that group starts at an aligned address. For this reason, we add some padding after the page list. With these three padding we are sure that cluster groups pages are always aligned to the block size.

3.2 Zero-Copy Merge

The second step in our implementation is the actual merge. It works at cluster group level, meaning that we add the columns of one cluster group at time to the resulting merged RNTuple. This cluster group granularity is necessary as we need to update the metadata of a cluster group before to start merging the next cluster group. Concretely, the content merging happens by calling a system call available on Linux system called `copy_file_range`. It is an extension of `ioctl` system call we described above. In fact, it has the advantage of managing the file blocks copy differently depending on the underlying file system. If the latter provides support for block sharing, then then blocks will only be shared between file, resulting in zero-copy overhead. The result is identical to `ioctl`¹. In case the file system does not provide this functionality, a block copy will be performed. However, even in the second case, this copy will result more efficient than performing several read/write, as the system call implements the copy at kernel level without passing through the userspace. The last step is the updates of metadata. Once we shared all the pages for a cluster group, we need to update its column and page offsets. All metadata are update in memory. When we merge two or more RNTuples, we create a new RNTuple descriptor. An RNTuple descriptor contains all the metadata. It stores information about header and footer; the clusters and how they are grouped in cluster groups and their page offset. When an RNTuple is committed on disk, the descriptor is serialized and written on file in form of header, footer and page lists. Thus, what we do is updating the RNTuple descriptor fields with the correct offsets, clusters and cluster group information. In other words, we preserve the structures of the source RNTuples in the merged one. Notice that we need

¹We do not use `ioctl`, as it would work only on XFS or btrfs file systems

to update the offset because data in each source RNTuple files has a local offset which would be different in the merged RNTuple. At this point, when the RNTupleDescriptor goes out of scope, the descriptor will be serialized on disk. This is the only write on-disk that the zero-copy merge performs. However, as metadata size is negligible with respect to the RNTuple data size, also its impact on the total execution time will be negligible.

4 EVALUATION

In this section we will present the experimental evaluation of our zero-copy merge implementation. We compare zero-copy merge with four alternative implementations by analysing their execution time and throughput. Specifically we compare `zero-copy merge` with its dual `kernel-copy merge`², `trivial-merge` and `fast-merge`.

4.1 Experimental Setup

All experiments are conducted using a 4-core Intel i7-h3770 CPU clocked at 3.4GHz and 16GB DRAM. All file accessed during the benchmark are stored on a 240GB SanDisk SDSSDHII Solid State Drive. The SSD is divided into two partitions of 100GB each, which are configured respectively with a XFS and EXT4 filesystems.

Both `ROOT`³ and the benchmark code are compiled with `-O2 -g` flags.

4.2 Execution Time Analysis

We start our analysis by comparing the execution time of zero-copy merge with the alternative implementations we presented at the beginning of this section. Figure 2 shows the execution time of the four merging implementations for different sizes of the input files. Notice that on the x-axis we report the sum of the two source files; the merging time on y-axis includes the sharing/copy of the RNTuple data content and the time for metadata updates. We run zero-copy merge on XFS as it is one of the file system currently implementing `reflink`. We compare it with other merging algorithm running on EXT4 file system. The reason why we chose to not run the other algorithms on XFS for the evaluation is that - as we mentioned - `kernel-copy merge` has the same codebase of zero-copy merge, while the behavior differs based on the file systems. Thus, in order to compare the `kernel-copy merge` with the zero-copy merge, we need to force the first one to copy data rather than just sharing them; we can do that running the algorithm on a file system which does not support block sharing, such as EXT4 file system. At this point, in order to make fair the comparison between the `kernel-copy`, `fast-merge`, and `trivial-merge`, we need to run all this algorithm on the same file system. As showed in Figure 2, the merge implementation executed XFS outperforms the other algorithms on EXT4 resulting in a almost constant merging time. Specifically, all the algorithms show an initial offset around 13 seconds. This is the time needed to read and copy the metadata from the two source RNTuples to the merged one. Then, the execution time of all algorithms grows linearly with the size of the merged files. However, the slope for the zero-copy merge is close to zero, as the main contribution to the execution time is given by the offsets updates. On the other hand, other algorithms have - in addition to time for metadata updates - the time for copy the content between RNTuples. As expected in the specific case of these experiments, the trend for trivial merge and fast merge is very similar. This is due to the fact that columns

²We call `kernel-merge` a zero-copy merge running on filesystem not supporting `reflink`

³<https://root.cern/>

in the source RNTuples are not compressed, so the trivial merge does not need to uncompress and compress-back data. Kernel-copy merge perform slightly better then fast-merge and trivial merge as data are copied at kernel level only.

Figure 2: Comparison between different merging implementations for different file sizes

4.3 Throughput Comparison

Having analyzed the merging time for the different algorithms, we analyze now their throughput, evaluating them in the specific case of merging two RNTuples whose sizes sum up to 25GB. Figure 3 reports the throughput in GB/seconds for the four merging implementations. Aside for the zero-copy merge, all other algorithms have a throughput, which is lower than the maximum throughput achievable on the device. Kernel-copy merge perform slightly better than fast-merge and trivial-merge. As the source RNTuples do not have compressed data, the throughput result

similar for trivial-merge and fast-merge. It is interesting to notice that with zero-copy merge, the throughput is two orders of magnitude higher than the device limit. This is due to the fact that the RNTuple columns are just shared and no data transfer is actually performed. This analysis clearly shows the advantage of using zero-copy merge over its counterparts.

Figure 3: Comparison of throughput in merging two files for a total size of 25GB

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work we provided an overview of four possible implementations for RNTuple merging algorithm. We presented a first implementation of a zero-copy merge and we evaluated it by comparing it with other less efficient merging implementations. We showed that our algorithm outperforms other implementations both for execution time and for throughput. Although the good performances, many challenges are still open. (1) First, the current implementation assumes that file systems have a block size of 4KB. However, this is not always the case. It is important to evaluate the algorithm and extending it to cases in which the block size is different from the default one. (2) Second, we assumed that all the pages for the same RNTuple are adjacent on disk. However, clusters in RNTuples can be interleaved by pages of other RNTuples. (3) Moreover, we are also assuming that RNTuples are saved and merged on traditional files. However, ROOT7 can support different storage backends, such as object store Intel DAOS. How the merging change when we are not using traditional file systems? (4) Finally, in the case of RNTuples having different compression settings, which one will be adopted by the merged one? All these aspects open the way for future developments.

6 REFERENCES

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